

FACTORS THAT ENHANCE EMPLOYEE'S SATISFACTION WHEN WORKING AT ANYA HOTEL

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Abstract

The goal is to identify and assess the factors influencing satisfaction of staff at Anya hotel following the epidemic, thereby providing solutions to promote strengths and overcome weaknesses to help the business operate better, increase employee satisfaction with the business, and that is also the premise to help increase employee productivity and efficiency. Employee happiness is extremely important in human resource management. To be able to manage human resources, you must first learn about the views and ambitions of the company's personnel. Satisfaction stems from the pleasant emotional state and professional spirit that the human resource administrator fosters in workers.

Keywords: satisfaction, employee, hotel, human resource, business

1. Introduction

Impacted by the Covid 19 outbreak, notwithstanding the present condition. The outbreak is still difficult, but in general, it has been kept under rather steady control. The tourism business, notably the hotel and restaurant industry, has thrived, thus hotels require a large number of employees to return. Employee happiness is the most crucial aspect in providing the finest experience to clients; this is certainly a deep statement. Because employee happiness has an influence on all parts of a company's operations. Many distinct elements influence employee satisfaction. This study reveals that the five primary elements influencing employee satisfaction are salary, leaders, advancement possibilities, and coworkers. Furthermore, it is a clear reality that no firm can reach its goals without the correct people, and this is the key to the company's success. This is why organizations invest so much effort into candidate selection and frequently employ closing questions to learn about the candidate's requirements and ambitions. When a candidate becomes an actual employee, however, relatively few firms are prepared to invest time and effort in learning about their emotions, wants, requirements, and satisfaction.

2. Literature review

One of the most essential variables determining the success or failure of a firm is its resources. As a result, many researchers, including local and international, value occupational satisfaction. Spector (1997), job satisfaction is shown when employees enjoy their work and understand all parts of it. Price (1997), work satisfaction is the positive emotional orientation of employees toward the firm. Evans and Rauch (1999), work satisfaction comprises the sentiments that individual employees have when their requirements are satisfied. These requirements pertain to the workplace. Employee satisfaction with work is a key factor that influences work

efficiency and profitability in businesses. The JDI job description index (Job Descriptive Index) by Smith, Kendall, and Hulin in the book "Measuring Satisfaction at Work and Retirement" was first published in 1969. It is one of the most prominent and extensively used studies not only in the hotel business but also in many other disciplines. One of the most powerful metrics of employee job satisfaction pellets is the model. This scale has five components: (1) Work nature; (2) Training and advancement chances; (3) Leadership; (4) Colleagues; and (5) Wages. Abraham Maslow's needs hierarchy is a main principle that leads to the identification of inherent human wants in general. People are categorized into distinct ladders ranging from "bottom" to "top," representing the "basic" level of man's existence and progress as both a natural creature and a social entity. Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory is spelled Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory. Frederick Herzberg, a psychologist who was interested in the relationship between employee attitudes and job motivation, presented this notion. The two-times hypothesis that influence employee motivation. Workplace variables include both maintenance and motivation. The mechanism's personal influence on employees determines the level of job performance and dedication to the business. As a result, we have an overview model of organizational behavior. Job satisfaction analysis, job satisfaction is not just an individual mechanism for evaluating the results of a job individual results of employees, but also have to consider other aspects such as: Acceptance of work pressure, work motivation, ethics and character issues, legal issues of the organization, the issue of learning and implementing employees' decisions. Systematize the study on the aspects influencing employee satisfaction with the company for which they work. Total Based on the studies, there are two types of factors influencing employee satisfaction tablets, which are as follows: The following internal effect variables are related to the character of employees: time, working time, and the demand for self-affirmation in the team. A group of external influences from businesses, such as coworkers, Policy on remuneration, promotion, the environment, and working conditions

3. Research Methodology

The study used the technique of conducting in-depth interviews with three experts in the field: two professors specializing in Hospitality Management and one expert. The purpose is to collect their viewpoints and experiences in order to appraise and adjust to the study's scope and parameters. Using table questions for face-to-face surveys and online questionnaires for internet surveys, as well as delivering questionnaires to survey individuals via social networks, data may be collected. Following the collection of data, it will be examined using the statistical data analysis tool SPSS 20.0. Examine sample descriptive statistics once the data has been encrypted and sanitized. Cronbach's Alpha is a test reliability metric, and EFA (exploratory factor analysis).

4. Research result and discussion

Table 1: Demographics of Respondent (n=300)

Variable	Frequency	Percentage %
Gender		
Male	200	66
Female	100	34
Age		
From 15 to 25	50	17
From 25 to 35	250	83
Income		
Below 15 million VND	10	4
15 to 25 million VND	90	30
More than 25 million VND	200	66
Occupation		
Student	20	6
Buisness	100	34
Officer	100	34
Freelance workers	80	26

Table 1 shows that the majority of respondents were students aged 15 to 25 (17%) and 25 to 35 (83%). 4% earn less than 15 million VND each month. There is little difference between the two genders who participated in the survey, male (66%) and female (34%).

Table 2: Cronbach's Alpha

Variable	Observed variables	Cronbach's Alpha
Co-worker	5	.776
Empowerment	5	.695
Recognition	5	.738
Salary	5	.759

Table 2 demonstrates that all four independent variables and the dependent variable have Cronbach's Alpha larger than 0.60, with the qualifying Cronbach's Alpha ranging between 0.6 and 0.95. This model takes into account all of the observations. Cronbach's alpha is a measure of internal consistency, or how closely linked a group of things is. It is regarded as a scale dependability metric.

Table 3: KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.	.846	
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	1716.453
	Df	189
	Sig.	.000

KMO is a test used to determine the strength of the partial correlation (how the variables explain each other). KMO levels near 1.0 are considered desirable, whereas values less than 0.5 are considered unsatisfactory. The KMO and Bartlett's Test of Independent Variable results of KMO = 0.846 and Sig = 0.000 suggest that the test of the conceptual validity of the scale is adequate for performing analysis.

Table 5: Rotated Component Matrix^a

	Component			
	1	2	3	4
CW1	.791			
CW2	.725			
CW3	.730			
CW4	.755			
CW5	.761			
EM1		.771		
EM2		.732		
EM3		.754		
EM4		.767		
EM5		.781		
RE1			.763	
RE2			.747	
RE3			.721	
RE4			.763	
RE5			.712	
SL1				.714
SL2				.771
SL3				.754
SL4				.758
SL5				.711

The eigenvalues of four factors are all bigger than one, while the observed variables' factor loading coefficients are all greater than 0.6. As a result, the scale is quite dependable and may be used for regression analysis.

Table 6: KMO and Bartlett's Test of Dependent variable

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.837
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	211.731
	Df	10
	Sig.	.000

Table 6 shows that $KMO = 0.837 > 0.5$, indicating that factor analysis is appropriate for grouping variables together and that the data is suitable for factor analysis. Because the observed variables are related, the significance threshold for Bartlett's test is $sig = 0.000 < 0.05$. The KMO measure of sampling adequacy is a test that determines whether or not factor analysis should be used on the data set. The null hypothesis that the variables in the population correlation matrix are uncorrelated is tested using Bartlett's test of sphericity.

Table 7: Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	R	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.672 ^a	.617	.684		.35120	1.812

When doing the regression analysis, the results show that adjusted $R^2 = 0.684$, suggesting that the independent variable causes 68.4% of the change in the dependent variable, with the remaining 32.6% attributable to other out-of-model components and random error. Durbin-Watson coefficient = 1.812; there is no autocorrelation between 1.5 and 2.5.

Table 8: ANOVA^a

Model	Sum of Square	Mean Square	F	Sig
Regression	21.526	5.148		
Residual	23.231	.136	61.362	.000^b
Total	54.757			

$Sig = 0.00 < 0.05$ and $F = 61.362$ indicate that the model is consistent with reality, that the independent variables are linearly connected to the dependent variable, and that the multiple linear regression model fits the data set and may be used.

5. Recommendation

Increasing productivity and stabilizing the Enterprise's human resource base, Spend less time and money on hiring new personnel and training them. Businesses must enhance the elements of employee happiness in order to improve the working process since more devoted workers always try to perform better. Trust, honesty, two-way commitment, and communication between a company and its employees are the cornerstones of employee engagement. By raising engagement, you raise your odds of succeeding and hence raise output, and employee

pleasure. However, if the company lacks the proper human resource management rules and procedures, this coherence may be lost, reduced, or even exacerbated. Even just taking the time to thank staff for their efforts will keep them motivated and engaged. Ensure them that any effort or success at work is appreciated, both publicly and privately. Trust, honesty, two-way commitment, and communication between a company and its employees are the foundations of employee engagement. Increasing engagement implies raising your chances of success, which will raise output, output, and employee happiness. However, if the company lacks the proper human resource management rules and procedures, this coherence might be lost, reduced, or even exacerbated. Simply taking the time to recognize employees' contributions may keep them engaged and motivated. Show them that your appreciation for their efforts, whether in public or privately, is shown for any effort or accomplishment. Team objectives provide everyone a common aim to strive toward and promote better employee communication. Start groups that focus on various hobbies to provide employees opportunities to engage and get to know their coworkers. It may be a reading club, an intramural sports team, or merely a get-together for people who have similar interests. Engagement is not just based on pay. Paying a competitive compensation, however, may be quite beneficial in luring the best talent and maintaining employee motivation. Employees nowadays want to feel as though they are a part of something greater. Ask employees to contribute to a list of values that best describe the culture of your organization. Additionally, creating a solid company culture is successful in keeping people. Burnout is a certain result of working without balance. Discuss with your staff how to establish a healthy balance between their job obligations and personal obligations. One's ability to share their labor with others is delegation. The workload of the management is to be decreased. Additionally, it gives workers chances to show off their strengths and learn practical job-related skills. Before allocating tasks, managers must do reasonable calculations or study. Because if done properly, this will have a number of negative effects, including: Spending a lot of time but being unable to complete the task; and Delaying work by assigning it to incompetent workers. lowering the team's overall effectiveness and having an impact on the output of the task. Because one individual can not manage too many activities at once, delegation and delegation serve to boost overall productivity. Large projects, in particular, may be finished on time with the participation of a sufficient number of workers.

Providing open, honest, and positive feedback to an employee's exceptional job outcomes constitutes recognition at work. When workers are appreciated and enjoy their jobs, the business's KPIs all rise to amazing heights. Employee engagement with their work and the organization will increase when they are acknowledged at work. They could even consider their present position to be an integral part of their lives, which would make them happy. They will have a close working relationship with the business and recognize how their efforts contribute to success as a whole. Employees' faith in their bosses and the company will inevitably increase when management acknowledge great outcomes and accomplishments in their job. Employees will psychologically trust those who have accepted and valued their efforts. To gain recognition and awards according to their professional accomplishments, employees will work hard to acquire and enhance their skills, experience, and job ability. Employee learning may also be stimulated and improved by recognition at work. It makes

workers feel as though they need always learn how to respond to their work better. This benefits the workers and enhances the business's performance in general. One of the most frequent forms of employment acknowledgment in businesses is promotion. When a person is promoted, the organization as a whole and the individual employee will both recognize that the employee has a strong history and merits a new position, role, or even management position. The position and work function of the employee should be acknowledged, and their performance should be evaluated in light of, those roles' standards and specifications. This is a criterion that guarantees equity in employee appreciation and evaluation. On the other hand, making sure that employees are recognized fairly contributes to your company's progressive development of an open and equitable workplace culture and reduces internal disagreements.

Conclusion

Job satisfaction plays a crucial role in fostering overall pride and sustained employee engagement with the company. Some HR procedures or duties may have a direct or indirect impact on employee satisfaction. Businesses must thus have a thorough understanding of employee job satisfaction in order to develop solutions that will boost workers' sense of fulfillment at work. Dissatisfied employees may disseminate unfavorable information about the business outside. This will make others who wish to join the firm more apprehensive, and it will also harm the company's reputation. Therefore, it's critical for HR experts to pinpoint which employees are dissatisfied, figure out how to fix the issue, and go from a pessimistic mindset to a positive one. Job satisfaction promotes shared pride and a longer-term commitment to the company. It is a crucial component of an employee's life cycle. Employee satisfaction levels may be impacted directly or indirectly by certain HR processes or activities. As a result, HR must also bear in mind that employee satisfaction is influenced by the way the company is run, including its policies, senior executives, and corporate culture, and assist in gaining economic and cultural advantages. Other crucial elements include leadership vision, how well-respected individuals are, whether or not their career path is secure and clear, and whether or not their efforts are compensated appropriately. Businesses should thus pay attention to the aforementioned variables to aid in the future development of the organization.

Conflict of interests

None

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